

ALLERGIC DISEASES

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Abstract: *An allergy is a response of the immune system to substances that affect the body or come into contact with the body, such as animal dander, dust, or bee venom.*

Key words: *allergic diseases, allergy, reaction*

The substance that causes an allergic reaction is called an “allergen”. Allergens are present in food, beverages and the environment. Most allergens are harmless, meaning most do not cause allergies.

If an allergic person comes in contact with an allergen, the allergic reaction does not occur immediately. The immune system gradually increases sensitivity to the substance.

Over time, the body becomes more sensitive - this process is called sensitization.

Sensitization can last from a few days to several years. In most cases, the sensitization process is not complete and the patient has some symptoms, but no complete allergic reaction is observed.

When the immune system reacts to an allergen, it becomes inflamed and irritated. Signs and symptoms depend on the type of allergen. Allergic reactions can occur in the intestines (digestive system), skin, sinuses, airways, eyes, and nasal passages.

Symptoms of dust and pollen allergy include:

Nasal congestion;

Itchy eyes;

Itching in the nose;

Rhinitis;

Swelling of the eyes;

Aging of the eyes;

Cough.

Symptoms of skin allergies, such as eczema (atopic dermatitis):

Skin peeling;

Itching;

Dry skin;

Red rash on the skin.

Allergies to food (food) have different reactions:

Return;

Swelling of the tongue;

Irritation in the mouth;

Swelling of the lips;

Swelling of the face;

Swelling of the throat;

Stomach cramps;

Respiratory disorders;

Rectal bleeding (children rarely);

Diarrhea;

Anaphylaxis (anaphylactic shock) is a very serious, often life-threatening allergic reaction.

Human immunity responds to an allergen as a pathogen (external harmful substance) and tries to destroy it as a foreign bacterium, virus, fungus, or toxin.

However, the allergen is not harmful. It's just that the immune system is very sensitive to this substance. When the immune system reacts to an allergen, it produces antibodies called immunoglobulin E (IgE) to kill the allergen. It produces chemicals in the body that cause an allergic reaction.

One of these chemicals is called histamine. Histamine causes muscle contractions, including in the walls of blood vessels and in the airways. Histamine also helps in the secretion of mucus from the nose.

A person with allergies blames the allergen for the allergy symptoms - a friend's pet, plant dust or pollen. But they are wrong. The problem is not in the allergen, but in the immune system of the allergic person.

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